



About this site.

The most important reason for the creation of this project was the imperative to countervail the process of evident mental regression (Poleev, 2019) and incidental social disintegration which is attributed to several historical, geographical and psychological causes, and to establish an effective tool to prevent such [destruction](#) and decomposition in the future.

In order to overcome the current indecisiveness in this respect, I will bring together all admins, activists or moderators of the internet projects, citizens' initiatives or research groups from all countries responsible or considering themselves who are responsible for the convocation of national constituent assemblies, in order to collaborate and to coordinate such activities worldwide.

Cooperativeness, immanent to human nature, is a fundament of social organization and an origin of human intelligence (Wilson, 1975; Axelrod, 1984). Consequently, a reinvigoration of cooperativeness with respect to interactivity and communicability, i.e. sociality, is essential for social and intellectual perpetuation (Tesla, 1905; Poleev, 2016).

In order to substantiate the preceding statements and also to confirm of the veracity of my intention I would like to analyze the terms used in this context.

In accordance with the findings of Carl Abel (1884, 1905) and Sigmund Freud (1900), we observe antithetical meanings of primal words. For example, the English word 'assembly' originates from latin word '[assimulare](#)' which means:

1. to make one thing like another, to consider as similar, to compare;
2. to represent something that is not, as real, to imitate, to counterfeit, to pretend, to feign, to simulate.

On the other hand, dissembler is a synonym for pretender, from which the German word Prätendent is derived. In the discussed context it is worth mentioning the difference between synonymous verbs to gather, to meet, to assemble, to congregate, to congress and to crowd (around), as well as polysemic (and, in my view, superfluous) meanings of crowding for 'overpopulation' (Überbevölkerung), and congress for 'sexual intercourse' (Geschlechtsverkehr).

Due to cultural interference between Latin and Greek languages in ancient times, the Greek word mimesis should be mentioned here:

Mimesis (ancient Greek: μίμησις (mīmēsis), from μίμεισθαι (mīmeisthai), ‘to imitate’ from μῖμος (mimos), ‘imitator, actor’) is a critical and philosophical term that carries a wide range of meanings, which include: imitation, representation, mimicry, imitatio, receptivity, nonsensuous similarity, the act of resembling, the act of expression, and the presentation of the self.

Several other words used to designate and to understand interpersonal relationships should also be mentioned here:

Ancient Greek: κοινωνία (society, communion, community), συντροφιά (companionship, society, societies, bevy, camaraderie), σύλλογος (club, college, society), εταιρία (company, firm, association, society), αριστοκρατία (aristocracy, nobility, society), αλληλοβοηθητική εταιρία (friendly society), κοινωνία της αφθονίας (affluent society), στυλοβάτης της κοινωνίας (pillar of society), κοινωνία της ανοχής (permissive society).

Latin (500 BCE - 1700): congregatio (assembly, society, union, assembling), societatis, societatem, societate (affinity, alliance, communion, conjugal union, connection), societas (fellowship, partnership, affinity, alliance, communion), proceres (chiefs, magnates, prelates, leading men of the country, nobles), collegium (col, coll, College, community, guild), coetuum, coetus, coetum (assembly, band, company, crowd, encounter).

English word coalition has Latin origin: nom. [coalitus](#) ‘communion’, verb [coalescere](#) ‘to grow together with something’, ‘to unite’, ‘agree together’, ‘coalesce’, from cum (co-, com-, con-) with, together + [alescere](#) ‘to grow up’, ‘increase’.

The top-level domain .re was chosen for several reasons. Firstly, the word ‘reunion’ can be found in different languages and has similar meanings of great symbolic significance and relevance to the presented content. Secondly, [as pointed out early](#), words with the Latin prefix re have similar meanings like ‘back’, ‘again’, ‘regarding’, ‘with reference to’, for example: renewal, return, resurrection, recursion, replay, reflection, report, Revelation, revision, religion, revolution. This wide range of interpretability of the acronym makes the .re-domain attractive.

Finally, the top-level domain [constitution.fund](#) was chosen to represent the corresponding Fund (Russian: Фонд конституционного строительства, fund from Lat. [fundamentum](#)), whose mission should be to establish and to promote the constitutional order in Russia, on the Internet.

The aim of this project, re:starting from Easter week [A.D. 2017](#), is meant to be an antithesis to the maxim ‘divide et impera’ which has always been destructive in its consequences for society and

individuality. So let us overcome our division into states, religious denominations, political parties and other crowds based on false identities.

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